

METHODOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF MARKETING

Musayeva Shaira Azimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7070790>

Abstract. *In this article, the organization and implementation of the economic activity of the enterprise based on a logical approach, all the work is reversed to the direction of the movement of goods and the historical sequence, starting from the consumer, who is the lower link, studying his demands, moving towards the higher link - production, and "formation of demand" " was considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, market, activity, commodity movement, logical approach, consumer, demand, offer.*

МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ МАРКЕТИНГА

Аннотация. *В данной статье организация и осуществление хозяйственной деятельности предприятия основаны на логическом подходе, вся работа обращена по направлению движения товаров и исторической последовательности, начиная с потребителя, являющегося нижним звеном, изучение его потребностей, продвижение к высшему звену — производству, и «образование спроса»».*

Ключевые слова: *предприятие, рынок, деятельность, товародвижение, логический подход, потребитель, спрос, предложение.*

INTRODUCTION

Marketing methodology is a teaching about the structure, development and method of marketing science (research, activity), its organization and implementation, knowledge of its object and justification of its results, principles, rules, ways, methods, tools, stages, procedures, forms of implementation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is a complex intellectual system that includes principles, rules, methods, methods, tools, and information, and is designed to perform the following tasks:

- regulation of cognitive and practical activities of marketing;
- defining and justifying the object, subject, purpose, tasks, problems, place and role of marketing science (research, activity);
- defining and determining the basics, structure, concept, ideas, goals, directions, stages of marketing science (research, activity);
- determine the marketing style, methods and tools, their properties, relationships and structure, ways of rational application, effectiveness and development;
- determining and evaluating the methodological characteristics and possibilities, form of use, scope, limits, rules, and role of each tool included in the marketing style;
- adapting methodological tools to the characteristics and purpose of the object and subject of marketing science (research, activity), placing them in their place according to the role of each one, and systematizing them;
- development of the method of marketing science (research, activity) and determining the procedure for its application;
- empirical facts related to the object and subject of marketing science (research, activity),

determination of principles, rules, methods of data collection, regulation, analysis and formation of empirical knowledge based on them;

- to determine the principles, rules, methods of creating and developing marketing theory and to ensure the creation of theory and its development based on them;
- determine and ensure the development of the marketing theory and method in a mutually proportional and compatible manner;
- to determine and determine the principles, ways, methods, procedure of evaluating and putting into practice the results of marketing science and research.

It should be emphasized that marketing science (research, activity) moves, moves, develops with the help of its methodology, style, methods. But this can happen with the help of good methodology, style, methods, as well as skillful application of them.

RESULTS

According to the dialectic of opportunity and reality, its functions serve to realize marketing opportunities and turn them into reality. Marketing functions (the Latin word function means execution, implementation) are the external realization, manifestation, application of the important properties of marketing in the form of directions of its activities and possibilities. Therefore, the extent to which marketing opportunities are realized and to what extent their use depends on the organization and implementation of its functions, which objective factors are the existence and creation of necessary conditions, and subjective factors are the qualifications, skills, and abilities of specialists.

Blocks of theoretical, empirical, methodological, etc. functions can be distinguished in certain areas of marketing. The methodological possibilities of marketing are manifested in its following methodological functions and are realized with the help of them, that is, marketing:

- the concept and methodology of production and sales activity of the enterprise (firm);
- demand formation and stimulation methodology;
- method of coordination of supply and demand;
- entrepreneurship (business) methodology and philosophy;
- serves as the management concept of the enterprise (firm).

Marketing is primarily the concept and methodology of production and sales activities of an enterprise (firm). In accordance with them, marketing activities should be organized, implemented and developed based on the following main principles: 1) targeting the final results of production to the needs of consumers; 2) taking into account the need, the state and dynamics of demand, the market situation and conjuncture when making decisions; 3) maximum adaptation of production to market conditions and demand structure with a view to maintaining long-term consumer preferences, not just one-time value; 4) to inform consumers about the company's product, influence them with all means of communication in order to convince and persuade them to buy it; 5) marketing effectiveness from the final result of the enterprise's activity, first of all, assessment based on its market value; 6) not only to satisfy the need, but also to create it and seek to fully satisfy the consumer.

In the conditions of the market economy, any product is intended for the market, it is sold if it meets the demand of consumers and can bring a profit by taking the real price. The market activity of the enterprise (firm, entrepreneur) determines the directions of its entire economic activity and ensures the intended profit. Because its ultimate goal is to make a profit, which it

can achieve through consumers. Adam Smith, one of the founders of classical economics, noted that an entrepreneur serves consumers better when they act for profit than when they consciously serve their interests. Because the pursuit of more profit forces him to expand production, raise quality at relatively lower costs, adapt to changes in the market situation faster, make quick decisions.

DISCUSSION

The laws and principles of the market economy require a radical restructuring of production and sales activities, seller-buyer relations, and a change in their role and status. In the conditions of the market economy, the consumer has priority as a subject of free choice, the market (sales) activity of the enterprise is the leader, the production activity is the follower, and the producer and sellers perform the role of serving the consumer. Focusing the production activity of the enterprise (firm, entrepreneur) on the market, orienting it to meet consumer demand requires combining it with sales activities and raising it to the level of a single production-sales process. This task is performed by the marketing methodology covering all production, sales and management activities of the enterprise (firm).

The concept and principles of marketing require the organization and implementation of business activities based on a logical approach rather than a traditional historical approach. In a logical approach, all work goes in reverse to the direction of commodity movement and historical sequence, starting from the consumer, who is the lower link, studying his needs, moving towards the higher link - production, and the consumer rises to the top of the pyramid. Marketing methodology is based on this logical approach and serves to implement it. Because marketing, its concept, methodology is based on logically determined, legal relations and dependencies.

Marketing, by its essence, is an information system, providing two-way communication between the enterprise (firm, entrepreneur) and the market, consumers, and serves as the main functional tool that coordinates their goals, aspirations, actions, and interests. According to Arch Shaw, one of the founders of the marketing concept, marketing is a function that provides communication between the producer (seller) and the consumer (buyer).

According to the marketing concept, the terms of exchange are the reciprocity of supply and demand in terms of quantity, quality, assortment, value, space and time, the willingness of the consumer to buy, to offer what he wants and convince him that this will better satisfy his needs, to give a satisfactory answer to any of his questions. , a guarantee to return or exchange defective goods, etc. Buerda marketing methodology serves as the organizational-methodical basis of the modern coherent exchange technology, which coordinates the actions, operations, and works of the enterprise (firm, entrepreneur) related to exchange in the market.

An important goal and at the same time methodological function of marketing is demand formation and stimulation. In order to perform these tasks clearly, it is first necessary to define and separate the concepts of "formation of demand" and "formation of demand". The formation of demand is to be born and develop in its own way, based on its own laws and regulations, without artificial influence. But it is difficult to imagine the free formation of demand in the current conditions of increased competition and advertising, where consumers are bombarded with various information and influences from all sides. Of course, manufacturers, service providers, and sellers try to create and increase demand for their products, and the implementation of this task is entrusted to the marketing methodology as the most appropriate

methodological approach.

COCNLUSIONS

Demand formation is the process of influencing consumers in a specific manner with marketing tools and methods, creating a demand for a specific product (service) in them and directing it accordingly, moving consumers from one state to another. The concept and principles of marketing require consumers not to be coerced or coerced, but on the basis of free choice, to provide them with the necessary real information in terms of their freedom and interests, to explain, to convince and persuade them that it is beneficial for them to do so. Marketing is based on the principle of free choice in market relations and implies its realization. John Keynes, the founder of macroeconomics, analyzed the socio-economic life in totalitarian countries in the last century: that deprivation of personal choice is a great loss in a homogenous (totalitarian) state. It can be added to this idea that the limitation of free choice in monopolistic markets also harms the interests of consumers.

Demand formation is a multi-faceted, multi-stage complex process, and its effective implementation depends on the fundamentals of demand formation and development laws, ways, means, methods, procedures, time, place and other subtleties of influencing its subject, the buying state and mentality of potential consumers. requires good knowledge. Marketing can influence consumers with its tools and methods, give them additional energy, arouse their calm or dormant emotions, sharpen their needs, turn them into demands and increase their desire to satisfy them, persuading them to voluntarily buy goods (services). The effect should be such that the intended consumers should feel it, perceive it, assimilate it and respond to it clearly.

REFERENCES

1. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.
2. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
3. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
4. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
5. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
6. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5.
7. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH

IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793
Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.

8. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozikovich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
9. Azimovna M. S., Shohruxhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
10. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
11. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
12. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
13. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
14. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhruxhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.
15. Azimovna M. S., Shokhruxhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
16. Azimovna M. S., Shokhruxhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 392-399.
17. Musayeva, S. (2022). DESCRIPTION OF MODERN MARKETING RESEARCH METHODS IN THE MARKET ECONOMY. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 33-38.
18. Musayeva, S. (2022). IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING SERVICE IN ENTERPRISES IN THE CONDITIONS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and innovation*, 1(A4), 280-286.
19. Musayeva, S., & Raxmanova, A. (2022). ANALYSIS OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN JSC" KHOVRENKO" OF SAMARKAND REGION. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 130-134.
20. Musayeva, S. (2022). WAYS TO ORGANIZE AND DEVELOP MARKETING RESEARCH IN THE LABOR MARKET. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 99-105.

21. Musayeva, S. (2022). PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MARKETING DEVELOPMENT IN TEXTILE AND SEWING-KNITTING ENTERPRISES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 28-32.
22. Musayeva, S. (2022). MARKET OF HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND FEATURES OF ITS RESEARCH. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 89-94.
23. Musayeva, S., & Usmanov, F. (2022). WAYS TO DEVELOP MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN TOURIST ORGANIZATIONS. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 84-88.